

ISic0630

I.Sicily inscription 0630

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone (local)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2002.07.01; 2015.11.12 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Mazara

Place of origin (modern)

Mazara del Vallo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Mazara del Vallo, Mirabilia Urbis

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175815

EDR 081934

EDCS 5200285

Bibliography

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Napoli, F. 1923. Spigolature storiche di Mazara antica. Marsala. At 155-159
Jacques, F. 1990. Remarques sur Lucius Cassius Manilianus et sa Carriere.
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